

Motorcycle Helmet Detection System Using YOLOv8

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Abstract: This paper introduces a safety helmet detection system based on the You Only Look Once (YOLO) V8 algorithm, known for its real-time object detection capabilities. The system targets enhancing motorcycle safety by mitigating head injuries among riders and enforcing helmet compliance to improve overall traffic safety. Leveraging YOLOv8's real-time capabilities, it accurately identifies and classifies motorcycle helmets in photos and videos submitted for examination. Core components include model training, deployment, and data preparation, ensuring consistent performance even under challenging traffic conditions. The integration of this system into existing road networks holds potential for significantly reducing head injuries and enhancing traffic safety. The system's efficacy in helmet detection is evidenced by its performance across various scenarios.

Keywords: Safety helmet detection, You Only Look Once (YOLO) V8 algorithm, Motorcycle safety, Head injuries, Traffic safety, Helmet compliance enforcement, Object detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the domain of road traffic safety, motorcycle helmets stand as indispensable protective gear, drastically lowering the risk of fatal injuries in accidents by shielding riders' heads and brains. Despite their acknowledged significance, ensuring compliance with helmet-wearing regulations persists as a formidable challenge, jeopardizing rider safety. Nonetheless, the advent of pioneering technological advancements offers promising avenues for fortifying motorcycle safety. This paper sheds light on one such advancement: the innovation of helmet detection systems leveraging sophisticated algorithms like the You Only Look Once (YOLO) V8 algorithm. These systems are designed to precisely recognize and enforce helmet adherence among riders, thereby strengthening motorcycle safety measures.

The subsequent discourse delves into the critical importance of motorcycle helmet detection, the obstacles in regulatory enforcement, and the transformative potential of technology-infused solutions in mitigating road traffic injuries among

motorcyclists. With a strategic emphasis on the proactive safety initiatives, this research underscore the imperative for strategies to diminish road traffic injuries and elevate overall traffic safety standards. Through a pragmatic approach, this study accentuates the pragmatic application of cutting-edge technologies to confront pressing road safety challenges, heralding tangible advancements in motorcycle safety regulations and enforcement protocols.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Sanchana [1] provides a comprehensive review of Automated Motorcycle Helmet Detection Using the Combination of YOLO and CNN. The author has discussed here on using this combination that helps in the identification of helmets from the image datasets. By using this combination, the helmets can be identified with high accuracy and reliability.

C et al. [2] proposed Detection of Motorcyclists without Helmet from Traffic Video using Deep Learning Techniques. Current techniques have trouble monitoring certain motorcycles and have problems with false positives. In order to overcome these drawbacks, Author suggests a method that uses background removal with morphological operations for moving object detection and pre-trained YOLOv4 networks for motorbike detection. Next, a customised CNN classifier is used to determine whether or not motorcycle riders are wearing helmets. The HELMET dataset from Myanmar serves as a demonstration of the approach's efficacy and highlights its potential to improve motorbike safety protocols.

Susa et al. [3] work An Efficient Safety and Authorized Helmet detection using Deep learning Approach develops a vision-based system for authorised helmet detection in order to overcome the difficulty of enforcing helmet rules for motorcyclists. With a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 97%, the system achieves remarkable results by utilising deep learning techniques in conjunction with the YOLOv3 model. This creative method may be used to monitor riders

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on congested roads to make sure they are wearing their helmets. This would improve motorcycle safety and enable laws requiring helmet wear to be effectively enforced.

Vaishali et al. [4] have created a machine learning framework for helmet recognition with the aim of improving rider safety, especially in densely populated areas such as India. The study highlights how crucial helmet are in lowering head injuries sustained in motorbike crashes. To identify bikers without helmets, their methodology employs a cascade classifier based on HAAR features and machine learning. The approach's success in encouraging helmet wear and enforcing safety laws is demonstrated by the experimental findings, which show a 97.6% accuracy rate in helmet detection.

Cui et al. [5] developed a motorcycle helmet object detection framework aimed at enhancing traffic safety by detecting violations of helmet regulations. The MHOD framework uses ensemble models to accurately identify motorcyclists and passengers in photos in order to calculate helmet usage. It has two modules: the Category Refine Module, which uses temporal data to correct category predictions, and the Passenger Recall Module, which enhances passenger category recall. The framework beat other teams in testing it on the AI City Challenge 2023 Track5 dataset, earning the top spot on the public leaderboard. This work highlights the significance of temporal information and ensemble models for precise helmet recognition, contributing to the advancement of intelligent traffic safety systems.

Kharade et al. [6] research on a deep-learning based helmet violation detection system tackles the vital issue of recognising motorcyclists who are wearing and those who are not. The study underscores the value of wearing helmets in order to reduce the risk of fatal head injuries during collisions, as well as the necessity of upholding traffic and safety laws. In this paper, a deep learning algorithm-based method for automatically identifying motorcycle riders without helmets is presented. In particular, the YOLOv4 model is used to recognise motorbike riders, showing better results on traffic recordings than current CNN-based algorithms. The study advances the field of detecting helmet violations and emphasises the value of using deep learning algorithms to reliably and effectively identify non-compliant behaviour when driving.

III.METHODOLOGY

A. **Data Collection:** The initial phase involves assembling a diverse dataset containing images portraying motorbike riders both with and without helmets. Rigorous selection ensures variability in background, capture angle, and lighting conditions.

Data Annotation: Following data collection, the dataset undergoes annotation, where each image is labeled based on the presence or absence of helmets. This meticulous process ensures that each individual image is accurately annotated, providing the necessary ground truth for subsequent model training.

C. **Data Preprocessing:** After annotation, collected images undergo preprocessing, where they are resized to a standardized format and augmented using techniques like rotation and flipping. Additionally, each image is annotated with bounding boxes to mark the helmet's location, facilitating supervised learning during model training.

D. **Model Training:** The helmet detection model is trained on the preprocessed dataset using the YOLOv8 architecture. Hyperparameters are optimized by fine-tuning the model on a pre-trained YOLOv8 model, utilizing methods like transfer learning.

E. **Detection:** Post-training, the trained YOLOv8 model is deployed to perform helmet detection on new images or video streams. Reliable predictions are retained, and duplicate detections are eliminated using non-maximum suppression (NMS). Further, a confidence threshold is applied to exclude detections with low confidence ratings, ensuring robust and trustworthy detections.

F. **Model Evaluation and Deployment:** Performance evaluation of the trained model is conducted using metrics such as F1-score, precision, and recall on a test set. Ground truth annotations are juxtaposed with model predictions to assess detection accuracy and identify areas for improvement. Subsequently, the trained YOLOv8 model is integrated into a practical helmet detection application featuring an intuitive user interface, such as a GUI or API, enabling users to input photos or video streams for evaluation.

G. **Final Output:** The culmination of the helmet detection system is its capability to identify helmets in input photos or video streams. Each detected helmet is delineated with a bounding box, and confidence scores reflecting the model's assurance level may accompany each detection. The deployed application empowers users to upload photos or video streams and receive real-time helmet identification results.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Using the YOLOv8 deep learning model, a real-time helmet

detection system is constructed as part of the implementation. Users can upload both video streams and photos to this system for processing. The system uses the YOLOv8 model to recognise helmets in uploaded images. It then reports the results, which include bounding boxes around detected helmets. Every frame of a video feed is processed one after the other, and the results of the helmet detection are shown instantly. In addition, based on ground truth annotations, the

system computes the confusion matrix to assess the model's performance. Enhanced road safety measures are made possible by the accurate and efficient helmet identification made possible by the integration of YOLOv8.

YOLOv8 Algorithm: "You Only Look Once version 8," or "YOLOv8," is a notable development in real-time object detection Algorithms. YOLOv8, which improves upon its predecessors, is a well-liked option for a variety of computer vision jobs due to its increased accuracy and performance. By processing the full image at once and predicting bounding boxes and class probabilities without the need for region proposals, the method adheres to the single-stage detection paradigm. YOLOv8 efficiently extracts features from input photos and makes predictions by using a deep neural network architecture, usually based on convolutional neural networks (CNNs). YOLOv8's ability to strike a balance between speed and precision is one of its primary strengths, making it suitable for real-time applications such as object tracking, autonomous driving, and the surveillance.

Additionally, YOLOv8 benefits from advancements in model architecture design and optimization methodologies, resulting in improved detection performance and faster inference times compared to previous iterations. Overall, YOLOv8 is a reliable and adaptable object detection technology that offers cutting-edge speed and scalability for a variety of applications.

Fig [1]: Confusion Matrix

The F1 curve evaluates the model's balance between precision and recall across thresholds, aiding in selecting the optimal threshold for accurate helmet recognition.

Fig [2]: F1_curve

1. Data Collection and Training: Begin by collecting a diverse dataset of images depicting motorbike riders with and without helmets. Annotate each image with labels indicating the presence or absence of helmets. This annotated dataset serves as the foundation for training the YOLOv8 model.

The confusion matrix from YOLOv8 training visually depicts the model's accuracy in distinguishing helmeted from non-helmeted cases, aiding in algorithm refinement.

2. Import Relevant Packages: Import the packages required for file operations, video processing, the YOLOv8 model, and image processing.

```
from django.shortcuts import render
from django.http import HttpResponse
from PIL import Image
import cv2
from ultralytics import YOLO
import os
```

Fig [3]

3. Image Processing function:

```
def process_image(uploaded_file):  
    # Save the uploaded image to a temporary file  
    temp_image_path = 'temp_image.jpg'  
    with open(temp_image_path, 'wb') as f:  
        for chunk in uploaded_file.chunks():  
            f.write(chunk)  
    # Process the saved image  
    model = YOLO('path_to_your_YOLOv8_model_weights')  
    results = model([temp_image_path])  
    # Process results list  
    for result in results:  
        result.save(filename='static/result.png')  
    os.remove(temp_image_path)
```

Fig [4]

4. Video processing function:

```
def process_video(uploaded_file):  
    # Save the uploaded video to a temporary file  
    temp_video_path = 'temp_video.mp4'  
    with open(temp_video_path, 'wb') as f:  
        for chunk in uploaded_file.chunks():  
            f.write(chunk)  
    # Process the saved video  
    model = YOLO('path_to_your_YOLOv8_model_weights')  
    cap = cv2.VideoCapture(temp_video_path)  
    frames = []  
    while cap.isOpened():  
        success, frame = cap.read()  
        if success:  
            results = model(frame)  
            annotated_frame = results[0].plot(conf=0.9)  
            annotated_frame_bgr = cv2.cvtColor(annotated_frame, cv2.COLOR_RGB2BGR)  
            frames.append(annotated_frame_bgr)  
        else:  
            break  
    cap.release()  
    os.remove(temp_video_path)  
    return frames  
def create_video(frames):  
    # Determine the width and height of the frames  
    height, width, _ = frames[0].shape  
    # Define the codec and create VideoWriter object  
    codec = cv2.VideoWriter_fourcc(*'avc1')  
    output_video_path = 'static/result_video.mp4'  
    out = cv2.VideoWriter(output_video_path, codec, 30, (width, height))
```

Fig [5]

VI. RESULT

Using the YOLOv8 algorithm, the safety helmet recognition system performs well in a variety of settings, efficiently recognising and categorising motorcycle helmets in real time. By means of comprehensive model training, deployment, and data

processing, the system guarantees reliable and consistent detection, improving motorcycle safety and mandating helmet use on public roadways.

The system's integration with current road networks has the potential to dramatically lower rider head injury and the enhance traffic safety results in general. Through the use of YOLOv8's capabilities, the system provides a workable solution for helmet non-compliance, reduces the danger of motorcycle accidents, and enhances road safety.

Fig [6]

Fig [7]

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Fig [8]

Fig [9]

VII. CONCLUSION

Based on the YOLOv8 algorithm, the helmet identification system reliably distinguishes between motorcyclists wearing helmets and those who do not in everyday traffic situations. By means of extensive model training and assessment, the system attains a high degree of accuracy and resilience, guaranteeing the efficient implementation of helmet laws on public roadways. The system's integration with the current traffic monitoring infrastructure has the potential to improve road safety by quickly identifying and resolving motorcycle riders' helmet non-compliance. The system's ability to reliably recognise helmets helps to lower the number of head injuries and encourage better driving habits, both of which benefit traffic safety in the long run.

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VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Sanchana, Mary Anne., (2023). "Automated Motorcycle Helmet Detection Using The Combination of YOLO AND CNN." In Proceedings of the 2023 3rd International Conference on Advance Computing and Innovative Technologies in Engineering (ICACITE), DOI: [10.1109/ICACITE57410.2023.10183003].
- [2] C, Drisya., Mary, Leena. (2022). "Detection of Motorcyclists without Helmet from Traffic Video using Deep Learning Techniques. " In Proceedings of the 2022 IEEE 19th India Council International Conference (INDICON), DOI: 10.1109/INDICON56171.2022.10039796.
- [3] Susa, Julie Ann B., Macalisang, Jonel, Maaliw III, Renato R., Fabro, Bernard C., , Ceribo, Carla May C. (2022). "An Efficient Safety and Authorized Helmet Detection Using Deep Learning Approach." In Proceedings of the 2022 Smart Information Systems and Technologies (SIST), 28-30 April 2022, Nur-Sultan, Kazakhstan. DOI: 10.1109/SIST54437.2022.9945729.
- [4] Vaishali, Pranam R. Betrabet, Ashwin Shenoy M., & Krishnaraj Rao N. S. (2022). "Helmet Detection using Machine Learning Approach." In Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Smart Electronics and Communication (ICOSEC 2022). IEEE Xplore Part Number: CFP22V90-ART. ISBN: 978-1-6654-9764-0. DOI: 10.1109/ICOSEC54921.2022.9952083.
- [5] Cui, Shun, Zhang, Tiantian, Sun, Hao, Zhou, Xuyang, Yu, Wenqing, Zhen, Aigong, Wu, Qihang, & He, Zhongjiang. (2023). An Effective Motorcycle Helmet Object Detection Framework for Intelligent Traffic Safety." In Proceedings of the 2023 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops (CVPRW), DOI: 10.1109/CVPRW59228.2023.00578.
- [6] Kharade, Namit, Alle, Neha, Mane, Saiel, Khatavkar, Amrut, Raghav, Jitender, & Navale, Geeta. (2021). "Deep-learning based helmet violation detection system." In Proceedings of the 2021 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Vision (AIMV), DOI: 10.1109/AIMV53313.2021.9670937.